

GENERAL LECTURE 4

Composite Materials in Aircraft Structures

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ABSTRACT

In aircraft structures glassfiber has been used increasingly since 1955 in sailplanes and in helicopter rotorblades. Advanced composites, among them carbonfiber-epoxy, were introduced in the early 1960s. In spite of their superior mechanical properties these new materials are being accepted only reluctantly in the construction of military and particularly of civilian transport aircraft because of the financial risk posed by recent interpretations of the concept of product liability.

INTRODUCTION

When the General Chairman of the Fourth International Conference on Composite Materials asked me to present an invited lecture, I gave him the above title for two reasons. First, I have worked on aircraft structures most of my life, and second, aircraft have played an important role in the development of composite structures. An indication of this is that two thirds of the carbonfiber produced in the United States is purchased by the aerospace industry.

FIRST AERONAUTICAL USE

Composite materials were first used in aeronautics by builders of glider planes. (In this paper "glider" stands indiscriminately for a glider, a sailplane, or a soaring plane, and it simply means an airplane without a motor). In the minds of many soaring pilots, flying in composite sailplanes began when the Darmstadt D-36 Circe placed second in the world soaring championships in the Cotswold Hills in England in 1965. However, gliders developed at the universities of Stuttgart and Braunschweig in Germany flew before that year and first flight of a sailplane with a glassfiber sandwich shell fuselage took place in Japan in 1955. The designer of the plane was Professor Tsuyoshi Hayashi, the General Chairman of ICCM-IV.

THE LIGHT BLUE SOARERS

The Today LBS-2, that is the second Light Blue Soarer of Tokyo Daigaku (Tokyo University, whose color is light blue), flew for the first time on August 10, 1955. It had an externally-braced wood wing and a monocoque fuselage; both the fuselage and the struts were made of satin-weave volan-finished glass cloth manufactured by the Nitto Boseki company (boseki means textile). The fuselage was laminated of 6 plies and the struts of 8 plies. The LBS-2 had a span of 13.03 m (42 ft 9 in.), an aspect ratio of 10, a total weight of 289 kg (637 lb), and a

best glide ratio of 17. It was used as a two-seater training glider by the Aero Club of the University of Tokyo and it made over 2000 flights before it was retired.

The design of the plane was based on experience gained with spoilers built of fiberglass for the Todai LBS-1 glider in 1954, and on theoretical and experimental work done by Professor Hayashi and his students at Tokyo University. The development and construction were supported financially by the Nitto Boseki company, and Hayashi, as well as Yoh, a veteran sailplane designer and builder, were responsible for the design.

The LBS-2 was followed by the LBS-3 single-seater high-performance sailplane which flew for the first time on June 7, 1956, with veteran pilot Isamu Oda in the cockpit. It had a span of 16 m (52 ft 6 in.), an aspect ratio of 17, and a flying weight of 320 kg (705 lb). Its best glide ratio was 40 and its minimum sinking speed 0.59 m/s (1.94 ft/s). The LBS-3 had a cantilever laminar-flow wing of wood and a sandwich mono-coque fuselage whose core was balsa wood and whose faces were 2-ply fiberglass.

Of the designers of the LBS planes Tsuyoshi Hayashi was born in Iijima, Naganō Prefecture, in 1911, graduated from Tokyo University in 1935, and taught there until his retirement in 1972. Many of his numerous research papers deal with orthotropic plates of which an example is fiberglass-epoxy cloth. In 1954 he was the first president of the Japan Society of Reinforced Plastics, and in 1972 the first editor-in-chief of the Quarterly Journal of Composite Materials.

The wood wing of the LBS-3 was designed by Masao Yamana, a former naval officer, who graduated from Tokyo University in 1927 and taught airplane design there after 1952; he died in 1975. Keiso Yoh, a native of Taiwan and graduate of Taipei University, directed the Tokyo Light Plane Research Institute where he built the Tokyo University sailplanes. He died in Taiwan in 1965.

GERMAN FIBERGLASS GLIDERS

When normal activities commenced again in German universities after the ravages of World War II, two graduate students, Richard Eppler and Hermann Nägele, started the design of a glider at the Technical University Stuttgart in 1951. Eppler was born in Ulm in 1924 and studied aeronautics and mathematics in Stuttgart and Tübingen. From 1949 to 1955 he was assistant to Professor Richard Grammel in Stuttgart and from 1956 to 1968 he was scientific adviser to Ludwig Bölkow while also giving courses at the Technical University München. In 1969 he was appointed professor at the Technical University Stuttgart.

A good analyst, Eppler developed theoretically wing sections with very low drag in the entire range of flying speed of the glider. To build the glider light, he and Nägele adopted the sandwich shell construction of the De Havilland Mosquito. The core of the wall was balsa wood as in the Mosquito, but for the faces Eppler and Nägele chose paper rather than plywood, because the loads on a glider are much smaller than those on a fighter-bomber.

The development proceeded at a slow pace until the plans were shown to Wolf Hirth, the greatest German teacher of soaring and developer of soaring techniques. He advised the designers to throw away the plans and build a new aircraft using fiberglass textile for the sandwich skin. The advice was followed and the paper glider was burnt. The new glider which arose from the ashes of the first one was named Phoenix after the legendary bird of Greek mythology.

The Phoenix was built by members of Akaflieg Stuttgart, the flying club of the students at the Technical University Stuttgart. "Akaflieg" is an acronym for Akademische Fliegergruppe, that is academic flying group. Its members were registered students who spent their free time studying, designing, building, and flying airplanes and gliders. Before World War II the Akaflieg system flourished because of the broad concept of academic freedom pervading the German universities. There was no compulsion for the student to attend classes, there was little if any homework to do, and exams could be taken when the student felt ready to do so. Thus it was perfectly possible for a student keen on flying to neglect his studies and to spend most of his time in the Akaflieg shop and on the flying field. He would get his degree in six or seven years, if at all. After the war the government began to diminish this freedom gradually.

The Phoenix flew for the first time in 1957. The following year it was tested thoroughly by physicist-boundary-layer expert-soaring pilot Augustus Raspet at Mississippi State College and was found to have the excellent maximum glide ratio of 40. In spite of this, and although it won the German soaring championship in 1962, the Phoenix did not sell well and only eight of the model were built. It became quite popular, however, after the rights to its construction had been acquired by the company Bolkow Entwicklungen, and after it had been redesigned by the original design team augmented by Rudolf Lindner.

The founder of the company, Ludwig Bolkow, was probably the most important aeronautical engineer-industrialist in postwar Germany. Born in Schwerin in northern Germany in 1912, he studied at the Technical University Berlin, and during World War II worked for Messerschmitt Flugzeugbau. In 1948 he formed his own company which after several mergers and reorganizations developed into MBB (Messerschmitt-Bolkow-Blohm). He retired in 1977 as president of MBB, the largest producer of German aircraft of its time. But much earlier he had made a significant contribution to composite aircraft manufacture when he promoted the redesigned Phoenix which he called Phoebus after the sun-god of Greek mythology. The Phoebus flew for the first time in 1964, and by the time its manufacture was discontinued, 253 copies had been sold.

Glass, the raw material of fiberglass textile, was probably first made by man in the third millennium BC in western Asia, and continuous filaments of it were also drawn in ancient times. On an industrial basis fiberglass production began around 1932, and the Owens-Corning Fiberglass Company was founded for this purpose by the Owens-Illinois Company and the Corning Glass Works jointly in 1937. In Japan the Nitto Boseki company has been producing glassfiber and glassfiber textiles since 1938.

In the form of a thin filament glass is flexible and yet very strong. From intermolecular binding forces physicists have calculated that the strength (or ultimate stress) of such filaments should be about 1.5×10^6 psi (10.34 GPa). This value has almost been reached with fibers a few microns in diameter ($1 \mu = 39.37 \times 10^{-6}$ in.) Glassfibers manufactured for reinforcing plastics have typically a strength of about one-third the theoretical value, and a modulus of 10^7 psi (68.95 GPa).

When the filaments are spun into thread, and the threads woven into a fabric, a textile is obtained which can be used for curtains, upholstery, and the like. By bonding together several layers of the fabric with a synthetic resin on a mold and polymerizing the assembly, one can build excellent bodies for canoes, rowboats, sailboats, and for aircraft. This method of construction has the great advantage that it can easily produce complicated doubly-curved surfaces, just as the tailor can mold wool cloth to the body of a man.

Naturally the operations that transform the thin glass filament into a structural part of the glider cause a reduction in the strength and the rigidity of the material. First, the filaments are embedded in a high polymer, usually epoxy, whose tensile strength is low. The ratio of the volumes of the two is typically one in the final product. Secondly, most gliders are built of textile with the same number of threads in the warp as in the weft. Thus only one quarter of the volume of the material can consist of glass threads running in the direction of the main loads. Moreover, the filaments within the thread are twisted, and the threads are bent where warp and weft intersect. The total effect is that the ultimate uniaxial stress of a fiberglass sheet is only 55,000 psi (379 MPa), and the tensile modulus is 10^6 psi (6.90 GPa).

But this strength is still quite respectable if one remembers that the strength of the most popular aluminum alloy, 2024 T 361, is 68,000 psi (469 MPa) and that the specific weight of the aluminum alloy is 2.8 while that of fiberglass-epoxy is about 1.9 (the specific weights of glass and epoxy being 2.6 and 1.25). Thus the strength-to-weight ratio of the fiberglass-epoxy composite is higher by almost 20 percent than that of the aluminum alloy. At the same time the composite is better suited to the construction of sophisticated aerodynamic shapes.

This was recognized by Bjorn Stender of Akaflyg Braunschweig (in Brunswick, or Braunschweig, in northern Germany) when he saw the Phoenix in Wolf

Hirth's shop in Nabern near Stuttgart. Stender, a talented young designer born in Stockholm, Sweden, of Baltic German stock in 1934, built the SB-6, which flew in 1961, out of fiberglass-epoxy.

A third student-designed glider, the D-36 Circe, probably had even more effect on the development of fiberglass construction than either the Phoenix, or the SB-6. It placed second in the world championships held in the Cotswold Hills in England in 1965. This event can be considered as the beginning of the fiberglass revolution in glider design which was so successful that five years later, when the world championships were held in Marfa, Texas, 85 percent of the 79 soaring planes that competed had been manufactured of fiberglass. Moreover, three of the four designers of the D-36 became leaders in the German fiberglass glider industry after they had left their alma mater, the Technological University of Darmstadt. They were Gerhard Waibel, Wolf Lemke and Klaus Holighaus, who joined Alexander Schleicher in Poppenhausen in the Rhön Mountains in central Germany, Rolladen-Schneider in Egelsbach near Frankfurt on the Main; and Schempp-Hirth in Kirchheim-unter-Teck near Stuttgart.

But in the meantime an important weakness of fiberglass structures had come to the fore: the low value of the modulus of elasticity of the finished product which was quoted earlier as 10^6 psi (6.90 GPa). This compares unfavorably with about 10^7 psi (69 GPa) which characterizes aluminum alloys. The consequence of a low modulus is large deformations under loads which in turn lead to flutter and divergence, two kinds of aeroelastic instability, at relatively low flying velocities.

This was illustrated dramatically in 1963 when Björn Stender flighttested a glider of his own design, the BS-1, in rather gusty weather. In a glide of 300 km/h (186 mph) the right wing failed because of divergence. Stender jumped through the closed canopy but a broken piece of the structure cut the opening cord of his parachute and this most promising designer-flier fell to his death at the age of 29.

Of course, the speed of flight at which aeroelastic instability sets in depends not only on the material properties, but also on many details of the design. Engineers have learned, therefore, how to make fiberglass gliders safe as long as they do not fly very fast in a steep glide and modern sailplanes are designed to glide safely at 165 mph (265 km/h). However, even a speed of 165 mph (265 km/h) is very slow for a modern military plane or civilian transport and thus fiberglass is not suitable for the construction of today's advanced transports, fighters and bombers. This is the reason why researchers and engineers began to look for fibers with modulus values that exceed by far those that characterize glassfiber.

FIBERS OF HIGH STRENGTH AND RIGIDITY

The feasibility of the production of fibers of high strength and of high modulus of elasticity was established around 1963 and the development of production techniques and facilities was pursued energetically by the then commander of the Materials Laboratory of the U. S. Air Force at Wright Field, Colonel Lee Standifer. He wrote contracts under which industry built plants for the manufacture of fibers of boron, a metalloid whose specific gravity is only 2.4.

Standifer was supported fully by the founder and first commanding officer of the Air Force Systems Command, General Bernard Adolph Schriever. Born in Germany in 1910 and brought to the United States at the age of seven, Schriever obtained an engineer's degree in aeronautics from Stanford University in 1942 and became one of the youngest three-star generals in the U. S. Air Force. Boron fiber development was also pushed by Alan Mathieson Lovelace, a native (1929) of St. Petersburg, Florida, who received his doctorate from the University of Florida in 1954 and was director of the Air Force Materials Laboratory from 1967 to 1972. He continued to hold high civilian positions in the U. S. Air Force and in NASA (deputy administrator) and in 1982 he left government service to become vice president of General Dynamics Corporation.

The difficulty with boron is that it can be made into filament only by a vapor-deposition method at very high temperature. A thin tungsten filament is made to pass at slow speed through a chamber filled with vaporized boron and the

boron metal is deposited in solid form on the tungsten wire. The process is a slow one and the final filament obtained has a minimum diameter of 0.004 in. (about 0.1 mm). This makes the final product undesirably stiff for some applications.

On the other hand, the mechanical properties of the filament are almost incredibly high: the average tensile strength is 460,000 psi (3172 MPa) and the modulus of elasticity 58 million psi (400 GPa), (as compared to 80,000 psi (552 MPa) and 10.3 million psi (71 GPa) for 7075 T 6 aluminum alloy which is heavier as its specific gravity is 2.8). Even when manufactured into sheets of unidirectional boron-fiber-reinforced epoxy, and when equal numbers of sheets are stacked with their fibers running in mutually normal directions, the resulting crossply has a strength of 104,000 psi (717 MPa) and a modulus of 16.4 million psi (113 GPa).

These are still extremely high values if one remembers that the material weighs only about two-thirds as much as aluminum alloys. Hence boron-epoxy would be an excellent structural material if its price were not just as high as its mechanical properties. In 1965 one pound of boron fiber cost almost exactly as much as one pound of gold, close to \$600. It was expected that mass production would reduce the price, but not dramatically because the method of manufacture would always remain a slow and expensive one. Nevertheless, today boron is much cheaper than gold simply because in the meantime the price of gold has increased dramatically, namely by a factor of about 16: in 1980 one ounce of it cost as much as one pound did in 1965.

In Great Britain the development of fiber-reinforced plastics followed a different route. There the outstanding researchers Watt, Phillips, and Johnson of the Royal Aircraft Establishment (RAE) in Farnborough, Hants, concentrated their efforts on the development of carbonfiber composites.

William Watt studied chemistry in Edinburgh and joined RAE in 1936. He began working on carbon in 1952 and by 1963 he was producing high-modulus carbonfibers on a laboratory scale. Watt's coinventor, Lesley N. Phillips, studied chemistry in London and found employment with RAE in 1943; there he worked on reinforced plastics and sandwich construction. The third member of the team, William Johnson, was educated in Newcastle-on-Tyne and moved to the RAE in 1954.

In Japan a researchman of the Osaka Industrial Technology Research Institute, Akio Shindo, developed essentially the same process of carbonfiber manufacture. His method was adapted to industrial production and patented by the TORAY company so successfully that today this company supplies over 40 percent of the need of the world for carbonfiber.

Carbonfibers are produced by the controlled oxidation and carbonization of fibers of a polymer called polyacrylonitrile (PAN); this takes place while the fibers are under tension. The result is a fiber consisting of carbon atoms aligned along the axis of the fiber whose diameter is only about 0.0003 in. (7-9 microns). Normally several thousand such filaments are collected in a bundle called tow.

The tows can be woven into fabric as was done with fiberglass; but more often they are arranged parallel in prepreg (contracted from pre-impregnated) form on a sheet of film or paper, impregnated with a synthetic resin, nowadays usually epoxy, and stored in a refrigerator. The minimum thickness of the carbon-epoxy prepreg tape is 0.001 in. (0.0254 mm, which is only about one-quarter of the diameter of the boron filament). The user can lay up the prepreg tape in directions and lengths best suited to his purposes; this can be done by hand or by layup machines. Finally, the assembly is cured (that is, the synthetic resin is polymerized) at the prescribed temperature and pressure.

Another method of manufacturing fiber-reinforced plastic structures is by filament-winding. The carbon (or boron) thread is passed through a synthetic resin bath and is then wound on a mandrel in a preprogrammed pattern. After curing the mandrel is removed. This method has been used widely in the manufacture of light-weight pressure vessels.

Depending on the temperature and the duration of the oxydization and carbonization the carbonfiber has ultimate stress values ranging from 290,000 to

350,000 psi (2.0 to 2.41 GPa) and modulus values of 50×10^6 to 35×10^6 psi (345 to 241 GPa). The specific gravity ranges from 1.92 to 1.75.

Unidirectional composites, with 60 percent of the volume taken up by carbon and 40 percent by epoxy, have ultimate stress values between 145,000 and 200,000 psi (1.0 to 1.38 GPa) and modulus values between 26×10^6 and 17.5×10^6 psi (180 to 121 GPa). The specific gravity ranges from 1.65 to 1.55. When equal numbers of unidirectional composites are bonded together in two mutually normal directions, the ultimate stress and modulus values of the resulting sheets are slightly higher than one-half the values quoted. They are, therefore, high if one remembers that the specific gravity of the material is less than 60 percent of that of aluminum alloys.

But again, the trouble is the high cost of the material. In 1980 the Hercules company sold carbon-epoxy tape for about \$50 per lb (\$110 per kg) while the cost of glassfiber textile and cold-rolled aluminum alloy sheet was only \$3.50 and \$2.25 per lb, that is \$7.72 and \$4.96 per kg, respectively. It is anticipated that with increasing demand carbon-epoxy tape will sell for about half its present price by the late 'eighties. However, even at the present price it is worth while to use carbon epoxy in airplane design because the value of weight reduction is very high in aircraft as 200 lb (91 kg) saved permit an airline to carry an extra passenger. Over the approximately 15-year life of a transport the added revenue is significant. Airplane designers estimate that they can afford to pay anywhere between \$80 and \$300 for a reduction of one lb (between \$176 and \$661 for one kg) in the empty weight of a transport plane. Similarly, in military aircraft every pound of structural weight saved allows the addition of a pound of military equipment.

ADVANCED COMPOSITES IN MILITARY AIRPLANES

In the United States the armed forces promoted the use of advanced composites in aircraft structures because they anticipated reductions in the structural weight, and because any gain in weight makes it possible to install more armament and armor, or to carry more ammunition and fuel. They placed contracts with manufacturers for the development and construction of parts made of composites, and they tested these parts on the ground and in the air.

Thus by 1972 Grumman Aircraft had built stabilators for the F-14 fighter and stabilizers for the F-111 fighter-bomber with boron-epoxy surface layers to increase their rigidity. Similarly, Douglas had used graphite-epoxy in the flap and the stabilator of the A-4 shipboard attack bomber, and Northrop in the leading-edge section of the F-5 fighter. In Great Britain the Vulcan bomber of Hawker Siddeley Aircraft had been flying with graphite-epoxy air brakes.

The McDonnell Aircraft company had been experimenting with composite structures since 1967 but it began their series production only in 1971 for the F-15 Eagle air superiority fighter. The structure of this plane contains 43 lb (19.50 kg) of graphite epoxy and 188 lb (85.28 kg) of boron epoxy, but the two together make up only about 2 percent of the total weight of the structure.

In the F-15 parts of the vertical fin, the horizontal stabilator, and the rudder are made of boron epoxy while the speed brake is of graphite epoxy. The first airplane to have its main wing structure made of an advanced composite is the AV-8B Harrier II, a redesign of the Hawker Siddeley Harrier.

The Harrier design started in 1957 as the P. 1127 project in the Hawker Aircraft Company offices in Kingston-upon-Thames in England. In 1963 the company became part of Hawker Siddeley Aviation Ltd., which in turn was taken over by British Aerospace Corporation in consequence of the Aircraft and Shipbuilding Industries Act of 1977. The first production Harrier joined the Royal Air Force in 1969 and the plane's AV-8A version began service with the U. S. Marine Corps in 1971.

The AV-8B Harrier II was developed for the U. S. Marine Corps by the McDonnell Aircraft Company from the Harrier I with the aid of a licencing agreement from Hawker Siddeley Aviation. It is a single-seat, single-turbofan aircraft for close air support and interdiction missions capable of vertical or short take-offs and landings (V/STOL). It can be based on board small ships and on small fields close to the combat zone. The Harrier II is powered by the same

Rolls-Royce Bristol Pegasus 11 vectored-thrust turbofan engine as the Harrier I. Its maximum engine thrust is 21,500 lb (95,600 N); it is directed (or vectored) through four swiveling nozzles, two on either side of the aircraft. All the hot gases can be directed vertically downward to produce lift in VTOL operations; rearward to give thrust; forward for braking in flight; or in any intermediate direction.

The major changes made during the redesign of the Harrier were the use of a supercritical wing section, an increase in wing area by 14 percent, an increase in span by 20 percent, the introduction of large positive-circulation flaps and drooped ailerons, and the extensive use of composites in the structure: 26 percent of the structural weight is the weight of elements made of graphite epoxy, and their use led to savings in weight amounting to 480 lb (218 kg). The Harrier II has an empty weight of 12,750 lb (5783.30 kg), a maximum weight for vertical takeoff of 19,185 lb (8702.17 kg) and a maximum weight for short takeoff of 29,750 lb (13,494.37 kg).

The entire wing is manufactured of graphite-epoxy. Each coverplate is laid up of 12-in. (0.3048-m)- wide prepreg tape to form a single slab of 28 ft (8.53m) span tapering in thickness from 0.44 in. (11.18 mm) at the wing root to 0.10 in. (2.54 mm) at the wing tip. The coverplates are connected by eight shear webs made of corrugated (sine-wave) graphite-epoxy woven cloth, with the corrugations running normally to the plane of the wing, and by widely-spaced light ribs.

Early in 1982 McDonnell Aircraft Company was using 50,000 lb (22,680 kg) of composite material a year. It was anticipated that this figure would increase to 400,000 lb (181,437 kg) by 1986 when both the AV-8B and the F-18 Hornet will be in full production.

ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY TRANSPORTS

The development of the first three wide-body jet transports, the Boeing 747, Douglas DC-10, and Lockheed 1011, was so costly that many years were expected to pass before these companies would be able to come forward with new designs. The planes were first put into scheduled passenger service in 1970, 1971, and 1972, respectively, and two more years passed before any competition arose to them in the Airbus 300 developed by a European consortium whose major partners are France, Germany, and Great Britain.

Shortly after the first scheduled flights of the wide-body jets, on October 16, 1973, the Organization of Petroleum Producing Countries (OPEC) suddenly raised the price of a barrel (containing 42 gallons that is 159 l) of oil in the Persian Gulf from \$2.10 to \$3.65. (The cost of production was estimated to be 10 cents). The increases continued through the years with the price reaching \$10.34 by November 1, 1974, and \$31.20 in March 1980. Because of this rise in the price of energy, and for other reasons, the economic activities of the world slowed down and eventually the economy slid into a recession. As many airplane transport and manufacturing companies experienced financial difficulties, the development and the sales of new aircraft lagged seriously.

But the changed conditions gave an incentive for the development of airliners that would utilize the energy of the fuel more efficiently. This led to the introduction in new transports of wing sections of lower drag, more efficient turbofan engines, and savings in the weight of the structure through the use of advanced composite materials. (In the United States the expression "advanced composite" means a fiber-reinforced plastic in which the fiber is of carbon, boron, Kevlar, or a combination of these, but not glass).

To further this development, NASA initiated in-house research in its laboratories and placed cooperative contracts with the Boeing, Lockheed, and McDonnell Douglas companies for the construction and testing of movable control surfaces for their transport planes.

Next, in 1978, the Boeing Company announced the construction of a family of advanced technology aircraft. The first of these, the 757, was developed for short-to-medium-distance transportation of 178 to 196 passengers. The 757 has a wing span of 37.95 m (124 ft 6 in.), an empty weight of 127,960 lb (58,042 kg), a maximum take-off weight of 220,000 lb (99,790 kg), and a range of about 2400 nautical miles (2763 mi or 4447 km). The power is produced by two high-bypass-ratio

Rolls-Royce RB.211-535C turbofan engines of 37,300 lb (165.9 kN) thrust each.

From the structural standpoint the interesting innovation is the introduction of advanced composites in the movable control surfaces: the ailerons, rudder and elevator are of graphite epoxy, and the spoilers are of Kevlar epoxy. Apparently Boeing is confident that these elements will have a lifetime of 55,000 h. At the same time their confidence is tempered with prudence because they are not using the new materials in the fixed control surfaces where their replacement, if necessitated by deterioration, would be much more time-consuming and expensive than in the movable surfaces.

It turned out that the structural weight of the 757 was reduced by 1490 lb (675 kg) through the use of 3340 lb (1515 kg) of composite material, and this reduction is expected to save 22,500 gal (85,163 l) of fuel a plane a year. (It is estimated that the plane will make 1400 trips of 1000 mi (1609 km) average length annually.)

Of course, the use of composites in the 757 (and the 767) is still very limited: it amounts to only 3 percent of the total structural weight. But this is already much more than the 0.5 percent on the Boeing 747. It is believed that composites may make up as much as 65 percent of the structural weight of transport planes in the 1990s.

Trends similar to those in America exist in Europe also where the Airbus company uses graphite-epoxy in its new models, the Airbus 310 and 320.

AN ALL-COMPOSITE AIRPLANE FLIES

An airplane all of whose major structural elements are made of graphite epoxy flew for the first time on January 1, 1981. It was the Lear Fan 2100, a low-wing executive monoplane whose two buried turboshaft engines drive a single four-bladed propeller in the rear of the fuselage. Learavia Corporation of Reno, Nevada, the builder of the Lear Fan, claims that the plane can carry six passengers and two members of the crew a distance of 350 mi (563 km) in an hour on 40 gallons (151.4 l) of fuel. This amounts to 8 1/4 mi per gallon (3.51 km/l) which is the same rate per person carried as 16 1/2 mi per gallon (7.02 km/l) for the family automobile accomodating four passengers in comfort.

Design of the Lear Fan was started by William Powell Lear, the inventor-industrialist who had brought out the eight-place Learjet in 1963. He sold his 60-percent share in the Lear Jet Corporation in 1967 and after trying out and disliking the life of luxury in retirement in Beverly Hills he moved to Reno to develop a steam-driven automobile. When this project fizzled, Lear founded the Learavia Corporation. After the death of Lear at the age of 76 in 1978, his fourth wife Moya Olsen Lear carried on the project as chairman of the board with Samuel H. Auld as president and J. Sheldon "Torch" Lewis as vice president for marketing.

The Lear Fan is powered by two Pratt and Whitney of Canada PT6B-35F turboshaft engines flat-rated to 650 shp (484.7 kW). Its wing has a span of 11.99 m (39 ft 4 in.) and an area of 15.13 m² (162.9 ft²). Its empty weight is 1656 kg (3650 lb) and its maximum takeoff weight is 3266 kg (7200 lb). The most economical cruising speed is 350 mph (563 km/h) at 41,000 ft (12,495 m). The Lear Fan was selling for \$1,600,000 in 1981.

The wing, fuselage, and the control surfaces consist of carbon-epoxy stressed skin reinforced with longitudinal and transverse stiffeners. The wing has three spars. The skin is laid up of sheets of textile woven by the Fiberite company out of Thornel carbonfiber manufactured by the Union Carbide Corporation. The thickness of the cloth is 0.013 in. (0.33 mm) and four layers are used for the thinnest, and 72 for the thickest skin.

There was more than the usual suspense at the first flight of the Lear Fan. One of the conditions of the \$50 million credit extended to Lear by the British government (for putting up the manufacturing plant in Northern Ireland) was a first flight by the end of 1980. The employees of Lear Avia worked 12-h days in the last weeks of 1980 to make the deadline but last-minute incidents thwarted them. The project was saved when the British purchasing commission extended the year by a day. Hank Beaird, manager of Learavia for flight operations, and

Dennis Newton, chief test pilot, flew the Learfan for 17 min. and brought back almost 60 lb (27.22 kg) of stamped envelopes to commemorate the flight: they were cancelled with a December 32, 1980 postmark.

THE FUTURE OF COMPOSITES IN AIRCRAFT

In the last two decades it has been said repeatedly that in aircraft structures composites would replace metals to a large extent in the near future. This prophecy has not yet come true and it is worth while to look into the reasons for the lack of a more extensive use of composites in the aerospace industry today. First, however, two kinds of aircraft will be mentioned in which composites are already in general use: they are helicopters and sailplanes.

One of the early builders of glassfiber helicopter blades was Bölkow Entwicklung in Ottobrunn, near Munich, Germany. Its counterbalanced single-bladed Bo 103 was successfully tested in 1961-62, and from this was developed the Bo 105 helicopter with flexible hingeless glassfiber blades first proposed by E. Weiland. After several mergers Bölkow became part of the Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm concern (MBB) in 1968. MBB has been cooperating with Sud-Aviation, and its successor Aérospatiale, which was formed in 1970 through a merger of Sud-Aviation, Nord-Aviation, and SEREB. These companies have been using glassfiber, and even carbonfiber, in their Puma, Gazelle, and Dauphin models developed, jointly with Westland, for the French and British military. Westland Aircraft was formed in 1935; it entered the helicopter field in 1947 with the aid of a licence arrangement with Sikorsky. Today, the blades of most of its helicopters have a stainless steel D-spar and glassfiber-reinforced plastic skin aft of the spar.

In the United States the Boeing-Vertol Model 107 flew for the first time in 1958. Its blades had a steel D-spar, aluminum ribs, and glassfiber skin. The Kaman Seasprite of 1959 and the Bell Iroquois of 1961 had blades of aluminum and glassfiber, and the Sikorsky S-70 of 1975 blades of titanium, glassfiber, and carbonfiber.

The success story of the glassfiber sailplanes has already been told. The somewhat unexpected new development in sailplanes is the use of carbonfiber-epoxy composites. It is unexpected because of the price of the material. But this difficulty was overcome by Akaflieg Braunschweig when the German military provided them with the carbonfiber needed for the construction of the middle portion of the wing of their large two-seater, the SB-10. The span of this glider is 29 m (95 ft 2 in.), slightly larger than the 93 ft (28.35 m) of the Boeing 737 transport. The aspect ratio of the SB-10 is 36.6, and its best glide ratio is 53. From the SB-10 of 1972 were developed the all-carbonfiber single-seaters SB-11 of 1978 and SB-12 of 1980.

After the success of Braunschweig with carbonfiber sailplanes the German commercial companies also began to utilize this superior material. The oldest among them was started by Alexander Schleicher in 1927; its designer Rudolf Kaiser (born in 1938) brought out the AS-W22 of 1981 with boundary-layer control over its relatively thick Wortmann wing section. Franz Xaver Wortmann (born in 1921) and his assistant Dieter Althaus have been developing wings of very low drag in the wind tunnel of the Technical University Stuttgart where Wortmann has been professor since 1968. The aspect ratio of the AS-W22 is 37, and its best glide ratio is 57.

The Schempp-Hirth company (founded in 1935) has two all-carbonfiber planes on the market, the 15-m (49 ft 3-in.) Ventus and the 22.9-m (75.13-ft) Nimbus 3. Both of them won championships in 1981, and both were designed by Klaus Holighaus (born in 1940), a successful businessman, outstanding designer, and excellent pilot. The LS-4 all-carbonfiber glider took the first seven places in the standard class at the 1981 world championships in Paderborn, Germany. It was designed by Wolf Lenke (born in 1938) and built by Rolladen-Schneider, a company engaged in the manufacture of window shades.

In Great Britain Roy Saunders of Slingsby Engineering in Kirbymoorside, Yorkshire, used both glassfiber and carbonfiber in the design of the Vega which flew for the first time in 1977. The company was started by Nicholas Frederick Slingsby (1895-1973) in 1930.

Apparently all these manufacturers have been able to sell their products in

spite of the cost although in 1982 the price of a carbonfiber competition sail-plane ranges from \$40,000 to \$55,000. But a first-class glassfiber competition plane also costs around \$30,000. The difference between the prices of sail-planes built of the two materials is bound to decrease in the future as the price of carbonfiber diminishes. It seems that Japanese manufacturers are already selling carbonfiber at prices considerably lower than the \$50 per lb (\$110 per Kg) quoted. In addition, the TORAY company and Union Carbide are making progress in improving the mechanical properties of carbonfiber produced from pitch which gives promise of further reductions in the price of fibers suitable for aircraft construction.

Nevertheless the manufacturers of large transport planes are very cautious in their approach to building the main carrying structure of their planes of carbonfiber because of the danger of failure, and the cost of providing for the possibility of failure. There was much less caution in evidence around 1930 when the reinforced monocoque aluminum alloy aircraft (the type of aircraft in general use today) was introduced because at that time, to a large extent, the purchaser bought the plane - or any other manufactured product - at his own risk. In order to recover damages after an accident he had to prove negligence or a breach of warranty on the part of the manufacturer.

In the last twenty years or so the decisions of the courts of law of the United States have established that the aircraft manufacturer is strictly liable for his product. That means that he is liable for damages caused by defects of the aircraft even in the absence of negligence on his part, that is even if he had designed and built the plane with due care and with full knowledge of the state of the art of aircraft design. Moreover there is no time limitation regarding product liability.

For instance, the wing spar of a large transport plane sold by a manufacturer to an airline may develop delaminations after ten years of use during which the plane will have flown 50,000 h. If the plane crashes and, say, 300 passengers are killed, the manufacturer is liable and the courts of California are likely to award damages amounting to a few hundred million dollars.

The risk involved in selling a new plane is therefore very high, and providing for the risk by means of insurance is very expensive. Thus the doctrine of strict liability is a powerful deterrent to a general introduction of advanced composites in aircraft construction. This deterrent can be overcome only through the development of a much better understanding of the behavior of composite materials and structures, and through improvements in the materials and the methods of manufacture. The Fourth International Conference on Composite Materials was called to make contributions in this direction.

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Fig. 1
LBS-3 of Tokyo
University. (Cour-
tesy of T.Hayashi)

Fig. 2
LBS-3 fuselage
fabrication.
(Courtesy of T.
Hayashi)

Fig.3. Phoebus A of Bolkow Entwicklungen. (Courtesy of George Uveges)

Fig.4. AV-8B structure. (Courtesy of McDonnell Douglas Corporation)

Fig. 5. Lear Fan structure. (Courtesy of Lear Avia Corporation)

Fig.6. AS-W22 of Alexander Schleicher Segelflugzeugbau. (Courtesy of C.Striedeck)

